

Solvent Extraction Studies on Mixed-Ligand Complex Formation of Vanadium(V) with N-Cinnamoyl-N-*p*-Methylphenylhydroxylamine and Thiocyanate Ion

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The extraction of Vanadium(V)-N-*p*-cinnamoyl-N-*p*-methylphenylhydroxylamine(I) complex in the presence of thiocyanate into chloroform may be used for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium in the presence of various diverse ions and also in steel samples. The extracted species, 1 : 2 : 1 V(V)-I-SCN complex, shows an absorption maximum at 590 nm with a molar absorptivity of 6.9×10^4 . Marked synergism is noted during the above extraction. The synergistic role of thiocyanate in the mixed ligand complexation has been utilized in the present work for the evaluation of the composition of the complex where both Job's and molar ratio methods are inapplicable. By extending the absorptiometric method the different equilibrium extraction constants (K_{ex} , K_A and K_{mixed}) have been evaluated.

SOME organic reagents and some arylhydroxylamines^{1,2} have been found suitable for spectrophotometric determination of Vanadium(V) even though several ions interfere in these methods. Ternary complexes of the metal with oxine and several anions^{3,4} have been investigated. Observing a marked influence of the thiocyanate ion on Vanadium(V)-arylhydroxylamine complexes, the present authors report in this paper studies on the mixed ligand complex of the metal with N-cinnamoyl-N-*p*-methylphenylhydroxylamine(I)⁵ and thiocyanate ions. The binary golden yellow complex of V(V) and I when extracted into chloroform at low acidity (*pH* 1.0) is found to be unstable and shows no λ_{max} in the range of 400-600 nm. However, a stable greenish blue complex is formed with SCN ion at low acidity range. The chloroform extract of the 1 : 2 : 1 [V(V) : I : SCN⁻] complex shows λ_{max} at 590 nm. Introduction of thiocyanate into binary sphere causes hyperchromic effect followed by bathochromic shift in the absorption maximum. The extraction behaviour of the mixed ligand complex and the evaluation of pertinent equilibrium extraction constants ($\log K_{ex}$, $\log K_A$ and $\log K_{mixed}$) are described here.

Experimental

Reagents, solutions and apparatus : The reagent I⁵ (m.p. 163°) was prepared following the method described in the monograph¹. The reagent was dissolved in A. R. chloroform. An aqueous solution of Vanadium(V) was prepared from A.R. ammonium metavanadate and the solution was standardised volumetrically⁶. All the chemicals, reagents, solvents, etc. were of A. R. grade. A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm glass cell was used for the measurements of absorbance. All *pH*-measurements were made with Elico (model L 1-10) *pH* meter.

Procedure for extraction of Vanadium(V) : An aliquot of Vanadium solution (100 μ g) was transferred to a separatory funnel (100 ml) and dilute hydrochloric acid and water were added to maintain the desired acidity (*pH* 1.0). The volume of the aqueous phase was adjusted to 15 ml. 5 ml of 0.1% reagent I solution in chloroform was added to maintain the final ratio of the aqueous to non-aqueous phase as 1 : 1. The contents were shaken for ~5 minutes (to attain equilibrium) when a golden yellow colored complex was completely transferred in the chloroform layer. 5 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate solution were then added and the mixture shaken for another 5 minutes. The resultant greenish blue complex was extracted, washed and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate and collected into 25 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up to 25 ml with chloroform and the absorbance measured at 590 nm against the solvent as the blank.

Procedure for high speed steel analysis : (BAS, 64b—containing 1.99% Vanadium) : The sample (0.6 g) was dissolved in dilute (1 : 4) sulphuric acid and the solution evaporated to syrupy mass on a hot plate. The process was repeated twice with 5 ml of the acid each time. Finally, the solution was treated with an excess (5 ml) of conc. H₂SO₄ followed by 2 ml of conc. HNO₃. It was evaporated slowly in a fuming chamber till the evolution of dense white fumes of SO₃. The contents were cooled and diluted to about 50 ml with double distilled water. The solution was warmed to dissolve any undissolved solid and was filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper. The residue was washed several times with hot water. The filtrate and the washings were collected and the volume made up to 250 ml with water.

2 ml of the above solution was transferred to a 50 ml beaker and Vanadium was oxidised at ~50°

with 0.1% KMnO_4 solution adding a few drops in excess. Following the general procedure, Vanadium was extracted from the mixture. Under these conditions Fe(III) was also transferred to the non-aqueous phase at pH 1.0. From the mixture, Fe(III) was removed to the aqueous phase by adding about 10 ml of 2N HCl. After a final washing with water, the chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous Sodium Sulfate, the volume made up to 25 ml and the absorbance measured. Subsequently, the percentage of Vanadium in the sample was determined. Vanadium found in the sample was 1.940%.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra: The dark-greenish-blue complex V(V)-I-SCN system, extracted into chloroform at pH 1.0 showed an absorption maximum at 590 nm. Since the reagents had no absorption in this region, further measurements were made using chloroform as the blank.

Effect of acidity: The maximum color intensity of the complex fully developed and remained constant in the pH range 0.5-2.0 and in the 2-4N HCl medium. Under both the conditions, the λ_{max} and ϵ value remained same. The studies, however, were made in the pH range (0.5-2.0).

Effect of thiocyanate concentration: Using 5 ml of 0.1% reagent I solution, 5 ml of 0.1% ammonium thiocyanate solution at pH 1.0 was sufficient for the development of maximum color for 4 ppm Vanadium. A very large excess of thiocyanate ions or adding thiocyanate simultaneously with I, decreases the color intensity of the system. Subsequent studies were made using 5 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate solution.

Calibration curve, optimum range and photometric error: The colored system was stable for 4 hrs at room temperature and obeyed Beer's law over the range of 0.5-12 ppm of Vanadium at 590 nm. The optimum concentration range evaluated from Ringbom's⁷ curve was 1-10 ppm. The per cent relative photometric error calculated from the Ayres⁸ equation was 2.70.

Molar absorbance and sensitivity: The molar absorbance (ϵ) value, calculated from Beer's law is $6900 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 590 nm and the corresponding Sandell's⁹ sensitivity is $0.0075 \mu\text{g v/cm}^2$.

Effect of diverse ions: The tolerance limit of Ti(IV) was increased substantially in the presence of NaF whereas Mo(VI), and W(VI) were tolerated to a higher extent. Interference due to Mo(VI) could be avoided by ethyl-xanthate extraction¹⁰. The tolerance limit of Cu(II) and Cr(III) could be increased by the addition of EDTA at low acidity and that of Zr(IV) and Nb(V) by adding phosphate. Pt(IV), Os(VIII), Re(VII) slightly interfered but their tolerance limits could be increased by adding excess thiocyanate solution. Fe(III) was completely extracted along with the V(V) complex at the pH range (0.5-2.0). Fe(III) can be removed either by increasing the acid concentration to (2-4N HCl)

or by extracting Fe(III) in ether from a 6-8N HCl medium. The ions with their tolerance limits in ppm within bracket are given below:

Fluoride (1000); Oxalate (1000); EDTA (1000); Tartrate (500); Phosphate (1000); Citrate (1000); Borate (1000); Thiosulfate (200); Mg^{+2} (200); Be^{+2} (200); Hg^{+2} (200); Al^{+3} (150); As^{+3} (150); U^{+6} (200); Th^{+4} (200); Mn^{+2} (200); Co^{+2} (200); Ni^{+2} (150); Cr^{+3} (150); Fe^{+3} (S.I)**; Ti^{+4} (I)*; Mo^{+6} (50); W^{+6} (40); Cu^{+2} (100); Zr^{+4} (40); Nb^{+5} (50); Ta^{+5} (100); Os^{+8} (10); Pd^{+2} (20); Pt^{+4} (10); Re^{+7} (20).

Evaluation of composition and equilibrium extraction constants of the mixed complex system: The ratio of metal to reagent (I) in presence of excess thiocyanate could be evaluated from both the Job's¹¹ and mole ratio methods¹² as well as from the extended absorptiometric method¹³⁻¹⁵.

To determine the ratio of V(V) to reagent I in presence of the fixed concentration of thiocyanate (5 ml of 2% ammonium thiocyanate solution) by Job's and mole ratio methods at pH 1.0 an equimolar solution ($9.825 \times 10^{-4} M$) of V(V) and I in chloroform were taken. The experimental plot indicated the V(V): I ratio as 1:2. This was further verified by applying the extended absorptiometric method. The plot of

$\log \frac{E}{E_{\text{max}} - E} - \text{pH}$ vs $\log [\text{HR}]_{\text{org}}$ gave a straight

line with a gradient of 2, indicating the metal: ligand ratio as 1:2 and $\log K_{\text{ex}}$ determined from the intercept on the ordinate (Fig. 1) and the value

Fig. 1. Composition and Extraction Constant (K_{ex}) of V(V)-I-SCN system.

S.I.** - Seriously interfere; I* - Interfere.

is 8.08, using the equations given below :

$$K_{ex} = \frac{[VO(R)_2OH]_{org}[H^+]}{[VO_2^+]_{aq}[HR]_{org}^2} = \frac{D_o[H^+]}{[HR]_{org}^2}$$

where $D_o = \frac{[VO(R)_2OH]_{org}}{[VO_2^+]_{aq}}$

and $D_o = \frac{E}{E_{max} - E}$ when E_{max} = maximum absorption

E = absorption for the amount of HR at the point in question.

Hence the above relation can be represented as :

$$\log \frac{E}{E_{max} - E} - pH = \log K_{ex} + 2 \log [HR]_{org}$$

Since under an equimolar concentration of $V(V)$ and thiocyanate, both Job's and mole ratio methods failed, the ratio of $V(V) : SCN^-$ were determined absorptometrically. The absorbances were measured by varying the concentrations of thiocyanate at 590 nm and pH 1.0, at a fixed concentrations of I (5 ml of 0.1% solution) and $V(V)$ of $7.86 \times 10^{-5} M$.

The plot $\log \frac{E_A - E_{min}}{E_{max} - E_A}$ vs $\log [SCN^-] - pH$ gave a straight line with slope of unity, indicating the $V(V) : SCN^-$ ratio as 1 : 1. The $\log K_A$ was thus obtained from the intercept on the ordinate of the same plot (Fig. 2) and the value was 3.60. Hence the $\log K_{mixed}$ ($K_{mixed} = K_A \cdot K_{ex}$) of the 1 : 2 : 1 complex is found as 11.68. The K_{mixed} was also determined directly from the plot of $\log \frac{E}{E_{max} - E}$ vs $2 \log [HR]_{org} + \log [SCN^-] - pH$. The

Fig. 2. Extraction constant of $V(V)$ -Thiocyanate (K_A of $V(V)$ -I-SCN system).

Fig. 3. Extraction Constant K_{MIXED} of Mixed Ligand Complex of $V(V)$ -I-SCN System.

plot also gave a straight line with the intercept value $\log K_{mixed}$ as 11.80 (Fig. 3).

K_A and K_{mixed} were determined using the following equations :

$$K_A = \frac{[VO(R)_2SCN]_{org}}{[VO(R)_2OH]_{org}[SCN^-][H^+]}$$
 which is equivalent to

valent to

$$\log \frac{E_A - E_{min}}{E_{max} - E_A} = \log K_A + \log [SCN^-] - pH, \text{ when}$$

$$E_A = \epsilon_1 [VO(R)_2OH]_{org} + \epsilon_2 [VO(R)_2SCN]_{org} \text{ and}$$

$$[V]_{org} = [VO(R)_2OH]_{org} + [VO(R)_2SCN]_{org}$$

and E_{min} = absorbance at $[SCN^-] = 0$, E_{max} = absorbance with large excess of thiocyanate.

$$\text{Again } K_{mixed} = \frac{D_{mixed}}{[HR]_{org}^2 [SCN^-][H^+]}$$

$$\text{where } D_{mixed} = \frac{[VO(R)_2SCN]_{org}}{[VO_2^+]_{aq}} = \frac{E}{E_{max} - E}$$

$$\text{Hence, } \log \frac{E}{E_{max} - E} = \log K_{mixed} + 2 \log [HR]_{org} + \log [SCN^-] - pH.$$

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